

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A Correlation study between Adjustment and School Environment among Secondary School Students

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***Abstract:** The present research deals with A Correlation study between 'Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students. The samples comprise 160 rural and urban Secondary School Students by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are 'Adjustment' Inventory for Dr.Pramod Kumar and School Environment Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The data was analyzed using r .*

Findings

There is significant correlation between 'Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students

***Keywords:* Adjustment, School Environment.**

Introduction:

The dictionary meaning of the word 'adjustment' is to fit, make suitable adapt, arrange, modify, the term adjustment is often used as a synonym for accommodation and adaptation. Adjustment can be defined as a person's interaction with his environment. Each person constantly strives to meet his needs and reach his goals. At the same time, he is under pressure from the environment to behave in certain ways. Adjustment involves the reconciliation of personal and environmental demands.

According to White (1981) 'Adjustment represents a compromise between the needs of the individual and demands of the society in which he/she lives. Individual tendencies must be restricted and channeled in certain directions if the person is to function as a member of the social organism. By the Dictionary of Behavioral Science, Wolman (1973) defined adjustment as follows "Adjustment is a harmonious relationship with the environment involving the ability to satisfy most of one's needs and meet most of the demands both physical and social that are put upon one". The variations and changes in behavior that is necessary to satisfy needs and meet demands so that one can establish a harmonious relationship with the environment".

The quality of education not only depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the school environment (Ajao, 2001)

The school environment is the major socialization institution for any child. It is the child's first contact with the world outside the house. A child spends 5 – 7 hours daily in the school. School environment is a foundation on which child's personality develops. Children learn proficiencies in various abilities like learning process and home work, social communications, handling emotions and the management of day to day interactions at home and schools

Hence the investigators selected the topic A Correlation study between 'Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students

Statement of the Problem

"A Correlation study between 'Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students."

Objective

1. To identify the correlation between Adjustment' And School Environment among Secondary School Students
2. To identify the correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among rural Secondary School Students.
3. To identify the correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among urban Secondary School Students

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students
2. There is no significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among rural Secondary School Students
3. There is no significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among urban Secondary School Students

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study of the Adjustment' And School Environment among Secondary School Students .The sample comprise for the present study is 160 Secondary School Students. Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data.

Tools -Adjustment' Inventory for Dr.Pramod Kumar and School Environment Questionnaire prepared by investigator.

Statistical techniques - The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Hypotheses:

- 1. There is no significant correlation between Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students**

Secondary School Students	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Adjustment	160	158	.77	.087
	School Environment				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is .087 and the obtain 'r' value is .77 So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among Secondary School Students.

Hypotheses:

2 To identify the correlation between Adjustment And School Environment among rural Secondary School Students

rural Secondary School Students	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Adjustment	80	78	.74	.217
	School Environment				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.217 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.74. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among rural Secondary School Students.

Hypotheses:

3 There is no significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among urban Secondary School Student

urban Secondary School Students	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Adjustment	80	78	.75	.217
	School Environment				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.217 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.75. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation

between Adjustment and School Environment among urban Secondary School Students.

Findings

1. There is significant correlation between Adjustment' and School Environment among Secondary School Students.
2. There is significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among rural Secondary School Students.
3. There is significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among urban Secondary School Students.

Conclusion

The findings of present study shows that the significant correlation between Adjustment and School Environment among Secondary School Students.

Reference

1. Best, J.W. & Kahn, J.V. (2006). *Research in Education* (9th Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
2. Kerlinger, F.N. (1979). *Foundations of Behavioral Research* (3rd Ed). New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
3. Kothari, C.R. (1990) *Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: Wiley Eastern Limited.
4. Mangal, S. K. (2002). *Advanced Psychology* (1st Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India, Private Limited.